

BUCKLING OF COMPOSITE PLATES WITH RECTANGULAR DELAMINATION

Meng-Kao Yeh¹ and Han-Chung Lee²
Department of Power Mechanical Engineering
National Tsing Hua University
Hsinchu, 30043 Taiwan, ROC

ABSTRACT

The buckling behavior of composite plates with rectangular delamination under compressive loading was studied analytically and experimentally. In analysis, a nonlinear finite element program based on the updated Lagrangian formulation was developed to analyze the response of the delaminated plates. The Newton-Raphson method was used to solve the resulting equation for the nonlinear system. A tensile-test machine was used to determine the load-displacement behavior of the delaminated plates under uniaxial compressive loading. The size of the delaminated region, the orientation of the fiber direction and the position of the delaminated region in the thickness direction were varied to assess their influence on the buckling behavior of the plates.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have been widely used in the automobile, construction, and weight-sensitive aeronautical and astronautical industries where high strength-to-weight ratio is needed. However, composite materials delaminate occasionally due to manufacturing defects, external impact or compression loadings during their service life. The delamination problem generally results in unexpected degradation of the structure. The problem of delaminated composite plates under uniaxial compression has been investigated in various ways. According to its position in the composite plate, the delamination in the composites can be classified into edge delamination [1-6] and central delamination. The central delamination can be grouped into the types of strip [7-22], circular [23-25] and elliptical [25-30]. The research about the delamination with corner, which are usually seen in the delaminated specimen, is very rare. Whitcomb and Shivakumar [31] used a virtual crack closure technique to calculate the distribution of the total strain-energy release rate along a square or rectangular delamination front. However, to our knowledge, the buckling problems of rectangularly delaminated plates are not reported.

In this study, we have investigated the buckling of rectangularly delaminated composites analytically and experimentally. In analysis, an updated Lagrangian formulation [32] was extended to derive the nonlinear finite element system equation for the delaminated composite plates under compressive loading. The problem was solved by a modified Newton-Raphson method by means of both the "load control" and "displacement control" procedures. The material properties of the delaminated plates used in the finite element analysis were obtained from experiment for comparison. Besides using the finite element analysis, we performed a series of experiments and the buckling modes were observed. For the cases considered, the specimens buckled first then followed by unstable delamination growth and loss of strength. Therefore, the buckling behavior

¹ Associate Professor, Author for Correspondence.

² Graduate Student

of the delaminated composite plates is the main concern of this study. The stacking sequences of the eight-layered composite specimens are $[\pm\theta_2^0]_{2c}$. Several parameters, including the position of the delaminated region in the thickness direction, the size of the delaminated region and the orientation of the fiber direction, were varied to evaluate their influence on the buckling behavior of the delaminated plates.

UPDATED LAGRANGIAN FORMULATION

As the composite plate undergoes large displacements and large rotations during buckling, the equilibrium equation of the buckling problem for the rectangularly delaminated plates is derived using the updated Lagrangian formulation [32]. As shown in Fig. 1, the body moves and deforms from an original configuration O to a current configuration S; all variables and the equilibrium of the body are updated to the current configuration S and used to obtain the next required equilibrium configuration T. The linearized equation of the problem is derived from the principle of virtual work.

$$\int_V C_{ijrs} e_{rs} \delta e_{ij} dV + \int_V \tau_{ij} \delta \eta_{ij} dV = \int_{A^T} P_i^T \delta U_i dA - \int_V \tau_{ij} \delta e_{ij} dV \quad (1)$$

where C_{ijrs} and τ_{ij} are the elasticity tensor and the Cauchy stress tensor in the current configuration. e_{ij} and η_{ij} are the linear and nonlinear parts of the strain increment tensor of the current configuration. P_i^T is the external force in the unknown configuration T.

FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

The three-dimensional hexahedral element was used in analysis. The coordinate of a generic point in the eight-node isoparametric element in the current reference configuration S is

$$\underline{X} = \sum_{k=1}^8 N_k \underline{X}^k \quad (2)$$

in which $N_k = N_k(r, s, t)$ is the shape function at nodal point k; \underline{X}^k is the Cartesian coordinate of nodal point k in the current configuration S. The incremental displacement of the interior point in the element from configuration S to configuration T is expressed in terms of the nodal point incremental displacement \underline{U}^k .

$$\underline{U}_e = \sum_{k=1}^8 N_k \underline{U}^k \quad (3)$$

There are three degrees of freedom at each nodal point. With the Jacobian matrix between the local coordinate (r, s, t) and the global Cartesian coordinates (x, y, z), the equilibrium Eqn (1) is expressed in the following matrix form.

$$([K]_L + [K]_{NL}) \underline{U}_e = \underline{P}_e^T - \underline{E}_e \quad (4)$$

in which

$$[K]_L = \int_V [B]_L^T [C] [B]_L dV \quad (5)$$

$$[K]_{NL} = \int_V [B]_{NL}^T [\tau] [B]_{NL} dV \quad (6)$$

$$\underline{E}_e = \int_V [B]_L^T \underline{\epsilon} dV \quad (7)$$

$$\underline{P}_e^T = \int_{A^T} [N]^T \underline{P} dV \quad (8)$$

In equations (5) - (8), $[K]_L$ and $[K]_{NL}$ are the linear and nonlinear parts of the element stiffness matrices, and $[B]_L$ and $[B]_{NL}$ the corresponding linear and nonlinear strain-displacement transformation matrices. $[C]$ is the incremental material property matrix with respect to the current configuration S. $[\tau]$ is a matrix and $\underline{\tau}$ is a vector of Cauchy stresses in the configuration S. \underline{P}_e^T is the equivalent force applied to the element in the configuration T. $[N]$ is the matrix formed by shape functions N_k . \underline{P} is the corresponding external force vector for P_i^T . Letting $[K]_e = [K]_L + [K]_{NL}$, we express the equilibrium equation of an element as

$$[K]_e \underline{U}_e = \underline{P}_e^T - \underline{F}_e \quad (9)$$

We assembled the element Eqn (9) to obtain the global system equilibrium equation as

$$[K] \underline{U} = \underline{P}^T - \underline{F} \quad (10)$$

in which $[K]$, \underline{P}^T and \underline{F} are the stiffness matrix, equivalent force vector of the configuration T and internal force vector of the configuration S of the global system. \underline{U} is the displacement increment from the configuration S to the configuration T.

MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Each layer of the composite laminate is assumed to be transversely isotropic [33-35]; the material properties vary according to its fiber orientations. Five material properties are needed to describe the material property $[C_c]$. The stress $\underline{\sigma}$ and strain $\underline{\epsilon}$ in the principal material fiber direction of each layer is expressed as

$$\underline{\sigma} = [C_c] \underline{\epsilon} \quad (11)$$

$[C_c]$ denotes the material properties of each layer. In each layer, fibers are assumed to make an angle θ with the r-direction of the natural coordinate (r, s, t). In the natural coordinate, the stresses $\underline{\sigma}_{rst}$ and the strain $\underline{\epsilon}_{rst}$ were obtained by transforming the stress and strain from the principal fiber direction as

$$\underline{\sigma}_{rst} = [T_1]^T [C_c] [T_1] \underline{\epsilon}_{rst} = [C^*] \underline{\epsilon}_{rst} \quad (12)$$

where $[T_1]$ was the transformation matrix between the natural coordinate and the principal fiber direction. Using the transformation matrix $[T_2]$ between the natural coordinate and the Cartesian coordinate, we express the constitutive relations of the composite laminate as

$$\underline{\sigma}_{xyz} = [C] \underline{\epsilon}_{xyz} \quad (13)$$

in which $[C] = [T_2]^T [C^*] [T_2]$.

NUMERICAL METHOD

For computational efficiency, the stiffness matrix $[K]$ in Eqn (10) changed only when a new displacement increment was added to the system. The modified Newton-Raphson iteration method was used to solve the nonlinear finite element equation. The load-control method was more efficient to increment the procedure before the delaminated plate buckled; because of the singularity of the stiffness matrix and the divergence of the numerical procedure as the plate buckles, the displacement control is an efficient tool to solve the problem near the buckling condition. This iterative process was repeated until a desired accuracy was achieved.

EXPERIMENT

The equipment used in the experimental procedure included a hot press, a tension/compression testing frame and a data-acquisition system operated on a microcomputer. The hot press was used to make the laminate specimen between the two platens through proper control of temperature and pressure. The carbon-fiber reinforced prepregs, properly layered and covered with bleeder and sealing rubber, were placed on a flat metal plate in an aluminum container. The pressure was applied on top of the rubber, while the gas accompanying the curing process was extracted by a vacuum pump. On the testing frame the specimens were placed between two fixtures. The upper fixture was connected to a load cell on the frame. The movement of the lower fixture was controlled by a DC motor and was as small as 0.35 mm/min for the experiments in quasistatic condition. The experiment was monitored by a data-acquisition system (Fig. 2). A typical experiment included one signal from the load cell and one from the displacement transducer in the loading direction. Two displacement transducers may be placed in the transverse direction for lateral displacement measurement as shown in Fig. 3. The signals from the load cell and the displacement transducers were connected to the amplifier and an AD converter in which the analog signals were converted into digital form and relayed to the microcomputer for analysis. Finally, the load-displacement behavior of the specimens was found and plotted for presentation.

The specimens used in the buckling experiments had length 140 mm, width 40 mm and 16 layers. The measured thickness of the specimens was 1.36 ± 0.08 mm. The length of the test section was 80 mm with 30 mm used for the fixture at each side. Rectangular teflon pieces (0.1 mm thick) were imbedded in the specimens at the ply interface to simulate delaminations. The stacking sequence of the laminate was angle ply with $[\pm\theta_2]_{2s}$. A diagram of parameter descriptions appears in Fig. 4. Several parameters, including the position of the delaminated region in the thickness direction, the size of the delaminated region and the orientation of the fiber direction, were varied to evaluate their influence on the buckling behavior of the delaminated plates.

In order to reduce the possibility of human error in the curing process and preparation of experiments, we tested three specimens in each case. The material properties of the delaminated plates were obtained from tensile-testing experiments and were used in the finite element analysis for comparison. The material property of each layer was assumed to be transversely isotropic [33-35]; five material properties, the longitudinal modulus E_{11} , the transverse modulus E_{22} , the shear modulus G_{12} and Poisson's ratios ν_{12} and ν_{23} are needed to describe the material property. ν_{23} is assumed equal to ν_{12} as conventional [5, 18]. Three experiments were performed for measuring each material property. The four parameters were measured to be $E_{11} = 104.6 \pm 4.0$ GPa, $E_{22} = 8.66 \pm 0.26$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.276 \pm 0.003$ and $G_{12} = 2.92 \pm 0.07$ GPa.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The material properties measured from experiments were used to analyze the delaminated plates in the finite-element formulation. The teflon insert used in the laminate to simulate the delamination was neglected in analysis. Three parameters, including the position of the delaminated region in the thickness direction, the size of the delaminated region and the orientation of the fiber direction, were varied to evaluate their influence on the buckling behavior of the plates. Comparisons were made between the experimental and analytical results.

Fig. 5 shows typical experimental load-deflection curves of the delaminated composite plate ($[\pm 30_2]_{2s}$, $a/L = 1/2$, $t/T = 1/2$) under axial compressive force. The ordinate was normalized by the Euler buckling load with 0° fiber orientation, $P_e = \pi^2 E_{11} b T^3 / (3L^2)$. The axial load increased linearly then reached a horizontal value called the buckling load. Sudden drops of the load caused by the unstable delamination growth can be observed from the experimental curve. The lateral displacements took off as soon as the composite laminate buckled. The two experimental lateral displacements kept the same distance together to show a global buckling mode. Therefore, it is reasonable to neglect the contact effect between the upper and lower delaminated regions of the

composite plates. In analysis, the plates were divided into three-dimensional hexahedral elements and a quarter of the delaminated plate is shown in Fig. 6. Fig. 7 shows three analytical load-deflection responses for specimen ($[0^0]_{16}$, $a/L=1/2$, $\nu T=1/2$) divided into 46, 78 and 104 elements, respectively. The three corresponding buckling strengths are 82.91, 75.01 and 73.70 N/mm². The difference between the later two cases was small; therefore, for computational efficiency the mesh with 78 elements was used for further calculations of the buckling strength of delaminated plates. Fig. 8 shows the corresponding analytical three-dimensional buckling mode and distribution of lateral displacement. The global nature of the buckling mode is similar to the one observed in experiment.

Fig. 9 shows the analytical and experimental results for specimens ($[0^0]_{16}$, $a/L=1/2$) with delamination located at various depths in the thickness direction. The buckling strengths decrease slightly as the delamination is located farther into the center of the laminates. Hence the buckling strengths are greater provided that the delamination is near the outer surface of the composite laminates. The worst case ($\nu T=1/2$) was then chosen for further discussion of different parameters, i.e., size of delamination region and orientation of fiber direction. Fig. 10 shows the analytical and experimental results for specimens ($[\pm 30^0_2]_{2s}$, $\nu T=1/2$) with various sizes of delamination. In the figure, the buckling loads decrease as the delamination size increases. The analytical results are slightly larger than the experimental ones when a/L is smaller than 0.4 and smaller than the experimental ones when a/L is larger than 0.4. Fig. 11 shows the analytical and experimental results for laminates ($[\pm \theta^0_2]_{2s}$, $a/L=1/2$, $\nu T=1/2$) with varied fiber orientations θ . The analytical results are above the experimental ones for smaller θ values ($\theta \leq 15^0$) and below and near the experimental ones for larger values of θ considered. For $\theta \geq 60^0$, the buckling loads decrease slowly as θ increases.

CONCLUSIONS

The buckling behavior of laminated plates with rectangular delamination under uniaxial compressive loading was studied experimentally and analytically. Buckling experiments were performed to investigate the influence of delamination on the buckling strength of the delaminated plates. A finite-element analysis was used to calculate the corresponding buckling strengths of the delaminated plates. Good agreement was obtained between the analytical and experimental results. The following conclusions are reached for composite laminates with rectangular delaminations.

1. For the cases considered, the buckling modes of the delaminated plates are of global type.
2. The buckling strengths decrease slightly as the delamination is located farther into the center of the laminates.
3. The buckling loads decrease as the delamination size increases.
4. If the stacking sequence of the composite laminates is $[\pm \theta^0_2]_{2s}$, the buckling loads decrease as θ increases.

REFERENCES

1. E. F. Rybicki, D. W. Schmueser and J. Fox, An energy release rate approach for stable crack growth in the free-edge delamination problem. *Journal of Composite Materials* **11**, 470-487 (1977).
2. B. D. Davidson, An analytical investigation of delamination front curvature in double cantilever beam specimens. *Journal of Composite Materials* **24**, 1125-1137 (1990).
3. S. S. Wang, Fracture mechanics for delamination problems in composite materials. *Journal of Composite Materials* **17**, 211-223 (1983).
4. S. S. Wang, Edge delamination in angle-ply composite laminates. *AIAA Journal* **22**(2) 256-264 (1984).
5. K. S. Kim and C. S. Hong, Delamination growth in angle-ply laminated composites," *Journal of Composite Materials* **20**, 423-438 (1986).

6. W. S. Chan and A. S. D. Wang, Effects of a 90° ply on matrix cracks and edge delamination in composite laminates. *Composites Science and Technology* **38**, 143-157 (1990).
7. D. Shaw and H. Y. Tsai, Analysis of delamination in compressively loaded laminates. *Composites Science and Technology* **34**, 1-17 (1989).
8. W. L. Yin, The effects of laminated structure on delamination buckling and growth. *Journal of Composite Materials* **22**, 502-519 (1988).
9. J. D. Whitcomb, Finite element analysis of instability related delamination growth. *Journal of Composite Materials* **15**, 403-426 (1981).
10. S. S. Wang, N. M. Zahlan and H. Suemasu, Compressive stability of delaminated random short-fiber composites, part I-modeling and methods of analysis. *Journal of Composite Materials* **19**, 296-316 (1985).
11. S. S. Wang, N. M. Zahlan and H. Suemasu, Compressive stability of delaminated random short-fiber composites, part II-experimental and analytical results. *Journal of Composite Materials* **19**, 317-333 (1985).
12. G. A. Kardomateas, Large deformation effects in the postbuckling behavior of composites with thin delaminations. *AIAA Journal* **27**, 624-631 (1989).
13. G. A. Kardomateas and D. W. Schmueser, Buckling and postbuckling of delaminated composites under compressive loads including transverse shear effects. *AIAA Journal* **26**, 337-343 (1988).
14. H. Chai, C. D. Babcock and W. G. Knauss, One dimensional modeling of failure in laminated plates by delamination buckling. *Int. J. Solids & Structures* **17**, 1069-1083 (1981).
15. G. A. Kardomateas, End fixity effects on the buckling and postbuckling of delaminated composites. *Composites Science and Technology* **34**, 113-128 (1989).
16. W. L. Yin, S. N. Sallam and G. J. Simites, Ultimate axial load capacity of a delaminated beam-plate. *AIAA Journal* **24**, 123-128 (1986).
17. J. W. Gillespie, Jr. and R. B. Pipes, Compressive strength of composite laminates with interlaminar defects. *Composite Structures* **2**, 49-69 (1984).
18. J. D. Whitcomb, Parametric analytical study of instability-related delamination growth. *Composites Science and Technology* **25**, 19-84 (1986).
19. S. L. Donaldson, The effect of interlaminar fracture properties on the delamination buckling of composite laminates. *Composites Science and Technology* **28**, 33-44 (1987).
20. E. Madenci, Delamination growth and buckling in an orthotropic strip. *Int. J. Solids Structures* **27**, 1773-1788 (1991).
21. G. A. Kardomateas, Postbuckling characteristics in delaminated Kevlar/epoxy laminates: an experimental study. *Journal of Composites Technology and Research* **12**, 85-90 (1990).
22. S. Sallam and G. J. Simites, Delamination buckling and growth of flat, cross-ply laminates. *Composite Structures* **4**, 361-381 (1985).
23. W. L. Yin, Axisymmetric buckling and growth of a circular delamination in a compressed laminate. *Int. J. Solids & Structures* **21**, 503-514 (1985).
24. W. J. Bottega and A. Maewal, Delamination buckling and growth in laminates. *ASME Journal of Applied Mechanics* **50**, 184-189 (1983).
25. J. D. Whitcomb, Three-dimensional analysis of a postbuckled embedded delamination. *Journal of Composite Materials* **23**, 862-889 (1989).
26. H. Chai and C. D. Babcock, Two-dimensional modeling of compressive failure in delaminated laminates. *Journal of Composite Materials* **19**, 67-98 (1985).
27. C. Kassapoglou, Buckling, post-buckling and failure of elliptical delaminations in laminates under compression. *Composite Structures* **9**, 139-159 (1988).
28. K. N. Shivakumar and J. D. Whitcomb, Buckling of a sublaminates in a quasi-isotropic composite laminate. *Journal of Composite Materials* **19**, 2-18 (1985).
29. S. N. Chatterjee, W. A. Dick and R. B. Pipes, Mixed-mode delamination fracture in laminated composites. *Composites Science and Technology* **25** 49-67 (1986).
30. M. K. Yeh and C. M. Tan, Buckling of elliptically delaminated composite plates. *Journal of Composite Materials* **28**, 36-52 (1994).
31. J. D. Whitcomb and K. N. Shivakumar, Strain-energy release rate analysis of plate with postbuckled delamination. *Journal of Composite Materials* **23**, 714-734 (1989).
32. K. J. Bath, *Finite element procedures in engineering analysis*. Prentice-Hall, New Jersey (1982).
33. R. M. Christensen, *Mechanics of composite materials*. Wiley, New York (1979).
34. R. M. Jones, *Mechanics of composite materials*. McGraw-Hill, New York (1975).
35. J. R. Vinson and R. L. Sierakowski, 1986, *The Behavior of structures composed of composite materials*. Martinus Nijhoff, Dordrecht (1986).

Figure 1. Motion of body in the stationary cartesian coordinate system

Figure 4. Parameter description of rectangularly delaminated composite plate

Figure 2. Schematic of data-acquisition system used for buckling experiments

Figure 5. Typical experimental load-deflection curve for rectangularly delaminated specimen ($[\pm 30^{\circ}]_2$, $a/L=1/2$, $t/T=1/2$)

Figure 3. Transducers arranged for measuring lateral displacements of the buckled specimen

Figure 6. Finite element mesh for a quarter of rectangularly delaminated composite plate

Figure 7. Analytical load-deflection curves for rectangularly delaminated composite plate ($[0^0]_{16}$, $a/L=1/2$, $t/T=1/2$)

Figure 9. Analytical and experimental results for specimens ($[0^0]_{16}$, $a/L=1/2$) with delamination located at varied depths

Unit : mm

Figure 8. (a) Analytical buckling mode and (b) Lateral displacement for composite laminates with rectangular delamination ($[0^0]_{16}$, $a/L=1/2$, $t/T=1/2$)

Figure 10. Analytical and experimental results for specimens ($[\pm 30^0]_{2s}$, $t/T=1/2$) with varied delamination size

Figure 11. Analytical and experimental results for specimens ($a/L=1/2$, $t/T=1/2$) with varied fiber orientations